

Hybrid membrane catalytic process for the hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds and simultaneous production of aromatic amines

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ABSTRACT

In the paper presented, a hybrid process that combines the catalytical hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) and the membrane separation using Donnan dialysis (DD) was studied. Four membranes used were composed with the interpolymer network (IPN) of polyethylene and poly(styrene-co-divinylbenzene), additionally functionalized with aliphatic or aromatic amines, and incorporating rhenium (Re) active sites. The proposed process was used for the conversion of selected nitroaromatics (NACs): 2-nitroaniline (2-NA), 4-nitroaniline (4-NA), 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (2,4,6-TNP) and nitrobenzene (NB). The offered process ensured simultaneous NACs hydrogenation and separation of the obtained aromatic amines (AAs) with the high molecular-level purity of the reaction product without residual NACs in the concentrate solution. For the analysis of reaction, the pseudo first-order model was used, the values rate constants (k_1) for the reaction were dependent on the type of feed solution and the membrane used. The highest value of this parameter reached $10.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for 2-NA, and the membrane functionalized with bis-3-aminopropylamine containing Re active sites. Besides catalytic reduction, this membrane enables effective separation of 50 % of resultant 1,2-diaminobenzene.

1. Introduction

Nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) are considered important group of chemicals produced mainly by human and industrial activities. NACs have attracted attention over the decades in relation to pollutants, toxicity, mutagenesis, carcinogenesis, therapeutic action, and intermediates in the synthesis of complex organic molecules. However environmental contamination has been a major focus [1–4]. Because of this, processes that might treat NACs-containing pollutants as substrates for the synthesis of aromatic amines (AAs) are particularly valuable. Such processes may not only mitigate the negative effects of NACs but also could lead to the synthesis of AAs that are highly valued chemical products, essential for the production of specialized chemicals, such as

large-scale pharmaceuticals and a variety of agrochemicals [5–8]. Conventionally, nitroaromatic compounds are reduced to AAs using chemical processes that are scalable from the laboratory to the industrial levels [9,10]. One of the ways to obtain this type of compound from waste containing NACs is to use heterogenic catalysts with metal nanoparticles (NPs) [11–14] or photocatalysts [15–17]. In this context, membranes processes involving catalytic functionality may play a particular role, as they may enable achieving a dual effect of catalytic NACs hydrogenations that may be further boosted by the separation of resultant AAs. In this context, a catalytically-aided Donnan Dialysis (DD) may offer a unique solution for the circular production-based approaches, in which a single process could serve as a tool for NACs remediation and AAs production.

Abbreviations: AA, aromatic amine; AExM, anion exchange membrane; NACs, nitroaromatic compounds; DD, Donnan Dialysis; IPN, interpolymer network; Re, rhenium; 2-NA, 2-nitroaniline; 4-NA, 4-nitroaniline; 2, 4,6-TNP, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol; NB, nitrobenzene; AAs, aromatic amines; NP, nanoparticles; 4-NP, 4-nitrophenol; 4-AP, 4-aminophenol; PE, polyethylene; S, styrene; DVB, divinylbenzene; AEP, 1,2-Aminoethylpiperazine; Bis3APA, Bis-3-aminopropylamine; API, 1-(3-aminopropyl)imidazole; CDI, 1,1'-Carbonyldiimidazole; ATR-FT-IR, attenuated total reflectance Fourier Transformation infrared spectroscopy; HRTEM, high-resolution transmission electron microscopy; HAADF, high-angle annular dark-field detector; SEM/FIB, scanning electron microscopy/focused ion beam; EDX, energy dispersive X-ray analyzer.

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Membrane processes based on Donnan dialysis (DD) are characterized by simple operation and low energy consumption [18]. Because of these features, the process has a high potential to purify waters from ionic contaminants as it was done previously for separations of *i.e.*, Cr (VI) [19] and Li(I) [20] ions. The driving force of the process is the chemical potential gradient of components of two solutions separated by a membrane. During DD, there is a stoichiometric exchange of ions of the same charge (counter-ions) through an ion-exchange membrane, and the process ends when Donnan equilibrium is reached [21]. In this process, the solution of the ionic species to be separated, such as an anionic species, is held in a feed chamber separated from a receiver compartment by an anion exchange membrane. The receiver chamber contains a high concentration of a stripping anion. The anion exchange membrane (AExM) prevents permeation of cations and allows diffusional transport of the anionic species from the feed to the receiving solution with an equivalent opposite migration of counter anions [18]. Although this process, like most membrane processes, has been used for a long time, new applications are still being sought, often as hybrid processes that combine the best properties of completely different procedures, *e.g.*, the microfiltration and sorption on resins [22]. This solution makes it possible to create combinations that allow to carry out its more efficiently.

In this context, the developed hybrid system presents one of the latest applications of DD through AExM functionalized with catalytically active rhenium (Re) active sites. The designed membranes allow to combine ion exchange separation with the catalytic hydrogenation of aromatic nitro compounds (NACs). The resultant hybrid process fits into circular production approaches, as it enables simultaneous catalytic reduction of NACs and production of pure AAs that are recognized as fine chemical products. In this work we continue the research on this hybrid process. In our former studies, we used a poly(chloride vinyl) membrane [11] functionalized with *i.e.*, 1,2-diaminoethane and Au nanoparticles (AuNPs) for the catalytic hydrogenation of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) and simultaneous separation of 4-aminophenol (4-AP). In this case the effectiveness of separation was low and this material had limited practical applications prospects. Thus, in our second approach, we have developed interpolymer network (IPN) membrane built on polyethylene (PE) and a copolymer of styrene and divinylbenzene p(S-co-DVB) with Re apparent NPs [12]. In this scenario, we successfully achieved 100 % of catalytic hydrogenation of 4-NP, and simultaneously, we were able to extract up to 50 % of 4-AP produced in the reaction environment [12]. The mechanism of this hybrid process involved the protonation of amino functionalities of produced 4-AP followed by ions transportation through IPN membranes, achieving a molecular-level purity of the reaction product. However, the established mechanism reveals a universal nature, and makes the process suitable for the catalytically-driven dialysis of other nitroaromatic compounds aimed at the production of desired AAs. In this context, in the present study we propose a series of processes enabling catalytic reduction of (2-NA), 4-nitroaniline (4-NA), 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (2,4,6-TNP) and nitrobenzene (NB) and separation of reaction products, namely, phenylenediamines, 2,4,6-triaminophenol, and aniline.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The reagents for synthesis of the polymeric membranes (monomers, amines), *i.e.*, styrene (S, 99 %), divinylbenzene (DVB, 80 %), 1,2-aminoethylpiperazine (AEP), bis-3-aminopropylamine (Bis3APA), 1-(3-aminopropyl)imidazole (API), 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole (CDI), were acquired from MERCK (Poland branch). The monomers (S, DVB) were purified before their use by vacuum distillation. Ammonium perchlorate (VII) (NH_4ReO_4 , >99 %), used for loading the polymer with ReNPs, as well as reagents for the catalytic activity test, *i.e.*, NaBH_4 (>99 %), 4-NA (>99 %), 2-NA (>99 %), 2,4,6-TNP, and NB were purchased from

MERCK (Poland branch) and used as received. All other reagents and materials mentioned in this manuscript were acquired from Avantor Performance Materials Ltd. (Gliwice, Poland) and used without any pre-treatment. All experiments were carried out using RO water (Merck, Milipore, Poland branch).

2.2. IPN membranes preparation

The procedure for the preparation of IPN membranes is detailed in ref. [12]. Briefly, the membranes containing functional groups derived from amines: 1,2-AEP, 1,3-API, Bis3APA, and CDI, were synthesized and further functionalized with Re apparent NPs. The latter step involved contacting IPN membranes with a NH_4ReO_4 solution (1000 mg L^{-1}) for 48 hrs, after which they were filtrated, and then washed and placed in H_2O . The functional groups derived from AEP, APA, API, and CDI led to the formation of a Re catalyst through reduction coupled adsorption of ReO_4^- [13]. Finally, the prepared membranes were coded using the codes of amines used for their syntheses.

2.3. Analytical and characterization methods

The membranes synthesized were characterized in order to confirm the amine functionalization process and the presence of Re apparent NPs in their structure. To confirm the presence of functional groups in the membranes, attenuated total reflectance. The change in the character of the membrane surfaces from hydrophobic to more hydrophilic was determined by the static contact angle measurements of water, using the droplet method, by a PG-X goniometer (Fibro Systems). Using the values obtained, the total surface energy of the membranes (γ_{total}) was calculated according to the harmonic averaging protocol (The Pocket Goniometer program version 3.4 with the ASTM D6946 method). Measurements were conducted for both areas of each membrane, namely for the one contacted with reagents during the catalytic process (herein named “*after reaction*”), and the second one without any contact with reagents (herein named “*before reaction*”), at least 3 membrane pieces collected from various places of a flat sheet membrane were tested.

To characterize the chemical structures of the synthesized membranes, the fourier transformation infrared spectra were recorded in the range of $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ using Jasco FT/IR-4700 (Medson, Paczkowo, Poland), equipped with attenuated total reflectance (ATR) attachment. The spectral data were recorded at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} by collecting 64 scans.

Concentrations of Re in membranes, after their wet digestion in a mixture of concentrated H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 , were determined via inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES), using an Agilent 5110 instrument (CA, USA). The morphology of the Re apparent NPs loaded into membranes was assessed using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM, FEI TITAN³, Thermo Fisher, MA, USA), equipped with a high-angle annular dark-field detector (HAADF), and operated in the scanning transmission electron mode (STEM). The membranes' surfaces were also analyzed using an energy dispersive X-ray analyzer (EDX, Octane Pro, Edax Inc.) as a part of scanning electron microscopy/focused ion beam (SEM/FIB, FEI Helios 450 HP, Thermo Fisher, MA, USA) measurements.

2.4. Process of catalytically-driven Donnan dialysis

The catalytically driven DD process was performed in a self-produced dialysis cell, which design and 3D printing protocol is detailed in our previous work [12]. At the beginning, the given membrane was placed between two parts of the dialyzer (see Fig. 1). Then the left chamber of the dialyzer was filled with 31 mL of a 0.1 mmol L^{-1} solution of a given NAC or NACs' mixture, while the right chamber was filled with 35 mL of a 1 mol L^{-1} NaCl solution. These solutions are referred to as feed (left chamber, Fig. 1), and concentrate (right chamber, Fig. 1) solutions,

Fig. 1. A scheme of the dialyzer used for the hybrid process of catalytic hydrogenation of NACs. The figure was prepared using BioRender under the license granted to Wrocław University of Science and Technology.

respectively. Four NACs were used in this process: 4-nitroaniline (4-NA), 2-nitroaniline (2-NA), nitrobenzene (NB), and 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (2,4,6-TNP). Additionally, the process with a NACs mixture was also performed. Next, to the feed solution containing a given NAC, 4 mL of a 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaBH₄ solution was introduced. This resulted in the initiation of the catalytic-dialytic process, which NACs contained in the feed solution began to reduce in the contact of the catalytic membrane. Simultaneously, during the reduction, the NAC was subjected to transport in a diffused form of aromatic amine (AA) through the AExM membrane in the direction of the concentrate solution. Throughout the DD process the solutions from both sides of the dialyzer were monitored using an UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Jasco V-630), recording spectra at fixed time intervals. Additionally, the pH of both solutions during the process was measured in the same time, using pH meter Endress + Hauser Liquiline (Germany).

This catalytic process was monitored and analyzed in the following way. First the UV-Vis spectrum of the feed solution consisting of NAC and NaBH₄ was recorded and the λ_{\max} was determined (see Table 1). As a result of contacting with the Re-loaded AExM, membrane absorbance at the certain λ_{\max} gradually faded and a series of new bands with absorbances at λ_{\max} 290–300 nm appeared. These were attributed to analogous AAs synthesized in the process. The process was monitored in that way for at least 16 h, by recording spectra at given time intervals. The above-described processes were carried out using single piece of

Table 1

The values of λ_{\max} of given NACs and AAs.

NAC (substrate)	NAC+NaBH ₄ λ_{\max} [nm]	AAs (product)
 1,4-diaminobenzene		
 1,2-diaminobenzene		
 Aniline		
 2,4,6-triaminobenzene		
NACs Mixture	275	NACs Mixture

each membrane. After a membrane's use, it was simply taken out of the dialysis chamber, washed with water and then re-introduced in to the subsequent run of the reaction.

The collected spectra were then collated and because an excess of NaBH_4 was used, it was possible to apply the pseudo-first-order kinetic model to the data. This allowed to determine first-order rate constants (k_1) of the catalytic process occurring in the feed solution. The calculations were performed with the assumption that the registered ratio between absorbance at the given time t (A_t) and absorbance at the beginning of the process (A_0) was proportional to the concentration change. As such, $\ln(A_t/A_0)$ plots were plotted against t , and the k_1 values were calculated from the slope of the above-mentioned plots.

In the concentrate solution, absorbances at λ_{max} in the range of 250–300 nm were assigned as isosbestic range of $-\text{NH}_2$ groups. These were further recalculated to establish AA transportation through AExM. For the calculations, it was assumed that the A_t/A_0 in the concentrate solution was proportional to the same ratio recorded in the feed solution. Based on these values, the $\Delta A(t)$ functions were established, and AA fluxes (%) were calculated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Re-loaded anion exchange membranes characteristics

To confirm the functionalization process of the polymer matrix of the starting sulfonated IPN membrane, the FT-IR spectra were recorded before and after amination. Spectra displayed in Fig. 2 show characteristic bands related to the N–H moieties, as well as rocking and stretching interactions for $-\text{CH}_2$ groups and C–C [23–26]. These confirm the successful modification of IPN membrane used as a polymeric matrix. At this point it must be also noticed that similar investigation was carried out previously [12] for the same samples but loaded with ReO_4 before and after reduction to Re active sites. In this case [12] there was a shift of

above-mentioned characteristic bands, suggesting the reduction of Re oxyanion. Because, ultimately, the present samples revealed catalytic activity, here the reduction of ReO_4 must had occurred as well [12,26].

The character of the surfaces of modified IPN membranes was studied by measuring the contact angle and surface energy. The contact angle values of the modified membranes were in most AExMs lower than 90° , which indicated that the surface character is hydrophilic; this was in the case of the membranes modified with 1,2-AEP, 1,3-API and Bis3APA (see Table 2). The different surface character was revealed in the case of CDI membrane that contact angle value was $>109^\circ$ (Table 2). This phenomenon results from the nature and chemical structure of the functional groups incorporated into the polymer matrix in the case of the CDI membrane which unlike other samples was characterized by the presence of 2 aromatic rings in its structure. The hydrophobic nature of CDI is anticipated to influence the efficiency of the hybrid process. This will be verified further in the manuscript. There is also a dependence between hydrophilic/hydrophobic properties of AExM and amount of Re loaded into them. In this context, the lowest Re concentration was also observed in the case of the CDI membrane (Table 2) that apparently might have limited access of ReO_4 to the polymer structure.

To verify, whether the Re concentration determined for the AExM (Table 2) is indeed associated with the loading of Re apparent NPs, all samples were subjected to the HRTEM/HAADF analysis. The Fig. 3 displays acquired images.

HRTEM pictures taken for all AExMs (Fig. 3) display well dispersed Re structures, occasionally grouped into clusters that appear to form particularly small NPs (~ 1 nm). However, the majority of these structures are characterized by sizes that fit below 1 nm, falling out of the definition of a “nanoparticle”. Hence, it may be concluded that Re active sites loaded into the AExMs took a form of apparent NPs. This outcome is consistent with our previous studies [7,12,14,19] where similar characteristics were observed. In this context, it is further anticipated that the tendency of Re to form particularly small structures will make the

Fig. 2. ATR FT-IR analysis of the membranes. (A) ATR FT-IR spectra, (B) list of specific bands location.

Table 2
Concentration of Re loaded and surface properties of the membranes.

Sample	Re concentration $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (%RSD)*	Contact angle [°] (after reaction)	Contact angle [°] (before reaction)	γ_{total} [mJ/m] (after reaction)	γ_{total} [mJ/m] (before reaction)
1,2-AEP	123 (4,0)	77.2	82.4	43.7	41.7
1,3-API	95 (3,8)	58.8	79.4	46.4	46.0
Bis3APA	247 (1,8)	73.1	69.4	47.0	46.9
CDI	<10	109.5	118.5	47.6	49.8
IPN (reference)	–	Contact angle [°] 77.0		γ_{total} [mJ/m] 37.2	

* Determined by ICP-OES [7].

synthesized AExM a good fit for the hybrid process of NACs hydrogenations.

3.2. The catalytically-driven hybrid process

The catalytically-driven DD process was carried out with the aid of membranes loaded with Re apparent NPs. These materials were used as separators between feed and concentrate solutions put in a custom dialyzer (Fig. 1). The hybrid process includes two-unit operations, namely (i) the catalytical hydrogenation that occurred in the feeding solution, and (ii) the dialysis transportation that separated the hydrogenation products in the direction of the concentrate solution. These two processes were simultaneous, but for better understanding, the results' analysis was divided into 2 phases. The first phase involved assessing the catalytical behavior of AExMs, which allowed to determine their catalyst characteristics in terms of reaction kinetics. The second phase dealt with what is called in this case 'dialytic transportation' in terms of the efficiency and unique mechanism.

3.2.1. What happens in the feeding solution (left chamber of dialyzer)

The catalytic hydrogenations of NACs occurring in the feeding solution were constantly monitored through the hybrid process. Fig. 4 shows the set of first order kinetics plots and UV–Vis spectra recorded in the left dialyzer chamber (Fig. 1).

According to the data shown in Fig. 4, the catalytic reduction of the NACs actually occurred in the feeding solution. The initial bands located at designated λ_{max} (Table 1) gradually faded and a series of new bands appeared (Fig. 4). The latter ones are associated with the emergence of the AAs structurally equivalent to the reduced NACs. The k_1 values determined for these processes were in the range of 0.3×10^{-2} to $10.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4, Table 3), the highest rate was recorded in the case of the Bis3APA membrane during reduction of 2-NA. This membrane simultaneously revealed the highest concentration of Re (see Table 2), and indeed, the catalytic reductions in the presence of this sample was generally faster as compared to other membranes (Table 3). Hence, the observed rate constant must have been proportional to the Re concentration loaded into AExMs.

It is worth noticing, that the lowest rates for most of the membranes (Table 3) were determined for the catalytic hydrogenation of 4-NA. In contrast, the hydrogenations of structurally similar 2-NA was performed much better (Table 3). Simultaneously, no such effect was observed in the case of the CDI membrane that unlike other membranes revealed a hydrophobic characteristics (Table 2). Based on this observation, it may be concluded that the difference between rates of 2-NA and 4-NA reductions must had been linked with the hydrophobic/hydrophilic characteristics of the membranes. In this context, the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups contained in the 2-NA and 4-NA may self-orient towards the hydrophilic membrane surface [27–29]. It means, that in the case of 4-NA the *para* position of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group would locate this substituent far from the Re active sites (see Table 1 for the NACs structures), resulting in decreased rate constants. Such a conclusion seems to be supported by the rates of 2-NA reduction (Table 3). Unlike 4-NA, the self-orientation of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group in 2-NA could make the *ortho*-substituted $-\text{NO}_2$ group accessible.

This may explain why the reduction of 2-NA proceeded much more efficiently as compared to 4-NA.

Based on the data displayed in Fig. 4 and Table 3, it may be concluded that the AExM enabled the catalytic reduction of NACs in both, single-component as well as multi-component solutions, in which all NACs were mixed together. In the latter case, as can be seen in Fig. 4 (last row) the bands at λ_{max} assigned to the isobestic point ($\sim 400 \text{ nm}$) of $-\text{NO}_2$ groups gradually faded like in the single component solutions and new ones appeared at $\sim 300 \text{ nm}$. In this case it could be also concluded that the overall rate of this process may be limited by the slowest hydrogenation occurring in the feeding solution, here, the reduction of 4-NA (Table 3). At this point it should be also noticed, that the membranes were applied subsequently in each hybrid process. The first use was in the catalytic reduction of 4-NA, the last was for the NACs mixture (in accordance to the order presented in Table 3). Despite each membrane was used 5 times, there is no observable decrease in their catalytic activity in the subsequent catalytical processes. This may indicate on a possible recyclability of the synthesized materials.

Based on the collected data further combined with yields (%) of NACs conversions displayed in Fig. 5, it can be stated that the hybrid process performance must be dependent mainly on surface characteristics of the membranes. In this context, hydrophobic membrane (CDI) revealed the lowest Re loading (Table 2), the lowest rate constants (Table 3), and aforementioned lowest conversions of nitroanilines (Fig. 5). The latter one, as was discussed above, can be associated with the self-orientation of $-\text{NH}_2$ groups towards membrane surface, that further hinders surface accessibility for the $-\text{NO}_2$ groups reduction. At this point, it is also worth noticing that the conversions of 2,4,6-TNF, NB and the mixture of NACs is almost on the same level for all of the applied membranes. In this context, there is no difference in conversion yields (%) when considering either, the type of a functional group or the amount of Re introduced into the membranes (Fig. 5 vs. Table 2). This observation allows to conclude that the hybrid process may be indeed a good suit for the processing of nitrophenols and nitrobenzenes.

3.2.2. What happens in the concentrate solution (right chamber of dialyzer)

At the same time as the process of catalytic hydrogenation occurred in the feeding solution, the concentrate solution was monitored. Fig. 6 displays UV–Vis spectra, which reveal a series of new bands that appeared as the catalytic process progressed.

As can be seen in Fig. 6, a series of new bands in the range of λ_{max} 250–300 nm appeared in the concentrate solutions. These can be assigned to the presence of the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups [30], and all the membranes were able to perform such transportation. However, in the case of the process carried out for 4-NA and 2-NA, a set of bands in the range of λ_{max} 380–410 nm emerged as well (Fig. 6). These can be attributed to the $-\text{NO}_2$ groups, meaning that the hybrid process carried out for these aromatics does not enable to produce pure amines, while in the case of NB, and 2,4,6-TNP it does.

The reason for this phenomenon may be associated with the mechanism of the hybrid process [12]. It involves the protonation of $-\text{NH}_2$ functionalities and their transportation within the osmotic flow occurring between feeding and concentrate solutions. As a result, the ions

Fig. 3. HRTEM/HAADF pictures of (A) 1,2-AEP, (B) 1,3-API, (C) Bis3APA, and (D) CDI samples.

Fig. 4. First order kinetics plots and UV-Vis spectra recorded in the feeding solution (left chamber of dialyzer) for the hydrogenations of 4-NA, 2-NA, NB, 2,4,6-TNP, and the mixture thereof. The panels display processes carried out with (A) 1,2-AEP, (B) 1,3-API, (C) Bis3APA, and (D) CDI membranes. Initial NACs concentration: 0.1 mmol L⁻¹. AExM contact surface: 19.625 cm².

produced within the process are dragged through the membrane in the direction of the right dialyzer chamber (Fig. 1). In the case of NB and 2,4,6-TNP, the $-\text{NO}_2$ groups, contained in these compounds, were reduced to $-\text{NH}_2$ groups (Fig. 4). Once formed, they are immediately protonated into the $-\text{NH}_3^+\text{Cl}^-$ form and transported towards the concentrate solution [12]. In the case of 4-NA and 2-NA, however, the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups are already there, even without the reduction of $-\text{NO}_2$ groups (see Table 1 for NACs structures). This means that nitroanilines

can be transported via the mentioned mechanism, and as an effect, some of unreacted 4-NA and 2-NA are detected in the concentrate solution (Fig. 6).

At this point, there is an interesting aspect to be mentioned. As stated in the previous subsection, the differences between catalytic performances of 4-NA and 2-NA reductions (Fig. 4) are related to the isomerism of these NACs (Table 1) that make the *para*-substituted $-\text{NO}_2$ in 4-NA less accessible for the reduction. It is because we hypothesize that the

Table 3
First order kinetics rate constants of NACs hydrogenations in the hybrid process.

NAC in feed solution	MEMBRANE							
	1,2-AEP		1,3-API		Bis3APA		CDI	
	$k_I^a \times 10^2$	R^{2b}						
4-NA	1.90	0.99	1.95	0.95	0.56	0.99	0.30	0.99
2-NA	2.42	0.99	1.38	0.99	10.55	0.98	0.38	0.99
NB	4.14	0.96	2.99	0.97	5.82	0.93	0.59	0.92
TNP	2.93	0.94	4.58	0.92	7.71	0.99	6.57	0.96
Mixture	1.94	0.98	1.27	0.96	1.71	0.96	1.68	0.98

^a First order rate constant (min^{-1}).

^b Correlation coefficient.

Fig. 5. Conversion rates of a given NAC in the hybrid catalytical dialysis process.

molecule orients itself towards membranes' surfaces through its $-\text{NH}_2$ group. It seems that this hypothesis is confirmed here, as when comparing the catalytic transportation of 4-NA and 2-NA, much more 4-NA is detected in the concentrate solution. Once NACs are dragged through the membranes by the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups (formed within the process or being already there), the *ortho*-substituted $-\text{NO}_2$ group in 2-NA is still better accessible for the reduction when compared to 4-NA.

The change of AA structures into the $-\text{NH}_3^+\text{Cl}^-$ form that is involved in the process mechanism, caused slight shifts of absorbances λ_{max} assigned to the amino functionalities from 290–300 nm (Fig. 4) to 250–300 nm (Fig. 6) [30]. Hence, to estimate the yield (%) of the AAs transportation, we needed to assume that the sum of absorbance values, attributed to the uncharged AA in the feeding solution and the charged AA in the concentrate solution, is proportional to the overall concentration of the given AA obtained. In this context, it can be estimated that 13–50 % of AAs produced in the feeding solution were transported to the concentrate solution (Fig. 7). However, at this point, we draw attention to the fact that this estimation must be treated with reserve when assessing the process carried out for 4-NA and 2-NA. In these cases, the estimated concentrations of amino-derivatives include also $-\text{NH}_2$ groups in the unreduced anilines.

Besides the hybrid process carried out for anilines (Fig. 3 and Fig. 6), the concentrate solution obtained as the result of NB and 2,4,6-TNP hydrogenations does not reveal bands associated with $-\text{NO}_2$ groups (Fig. 6). A similar observation has been noted previously [12] for the process carried out in the presence of 4-nitrophenol. Here, it can be

stated that the proposed hybrid technology may be a valid tool for the production of pure AAs from nitrophenols and nitrobenzenes.

4. Conclusions

Here, we proposed a hybrid process aimed at the simultaneous catalytic reduction of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) and membrane separation of resulting fine chemical products, *i.e.* aromatic amines (AAs). For the process, four nanocomposite membranes were applied. The membranes, containing functionalities derived from: 1,2-aminoe-thylpiperazine, bis-3-aminopropylamine, 1-(3-aminopropyl)imidazole, and 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole were further loaded with Re apparent nanoparticles (NPs) serving as highly active catalytic sites.

The obtained results shown that the Re-loaded anion exchange membranes (AExM) effectively catalyzed the reduction of NACs with pseudo-first-order rate constants ranging from 0.3×10^{-2} to $10.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The highest value of the rate constant ($k_I = 10.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$) was recorded for the hydrogenation of 2-nitroaniline, and the membrane with functionalities derived from bis-3-aminopropylamine. In turn, the lowest rate constant ($k_I = 0.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$) was determined for the 4-nitroaniline reduction process aided by membrane with functionalities derived from 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole. The yields(%) of NACs conversion and resultant AAs extraction was dependent on the hydrophilic/hydrophobic characteristics of the AExM. In this context, the lowest reduction efficiency was observed for the 2-nitroaniline reduction carried out with the aid of hydrophobic CDI.

The mechanism of hybrid process was explained with osmotic flow of ions between feed and concentrate solutions dragged NAC through the membranes. Within this process, NACs were simultaneously reduced into analogous AAs that were further protonated and transported to the concentrate solution. It was established that this mechanism causes the hybrid process is not suitable for processing of nitroanilines, as they can be transported through the membranes even without co-occurring catalytic reduction.

The proposed hybrid process combines the advantages of Re apparent NPs as a catalyst and AExM membranes. These materials operate as a selective catalytic-separator and offer an efficient, scalable, and economically viable solution for the concurrent reduction of NACs and molecular-level extraction of valuable AAs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Joanna Wolska: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Visualization, Formal analysis, Supervision. **Marek Bryjak:** Methodology, Resources. **Pawel Pohl:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Anna Dzimitrowicz:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Piotr Cyganowski:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: [Piotr Cyganowski reports financial support was provided by National Science Centre Poland. Joanna Wolska, Piotr Cyganowski reports was provided by Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Poland. Joanna Wolska reports financial support was provided by Wroclaw University of Science and Technology. Joanna Wolska, Piotr Cyganowski has patent Method of preparing hybrid anion exchange membranes for the dialytic-catalytic synthesis of aromatic amines and method of carrying out this synthesis pending to na. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

Fig. 6. UV-Vis spectra recorded in the concentrate solution (right chamber of dialyzer) during co-occurring hydrogenations of 4-NA, 2-NA, NB, 2,4,6-TNP, and the mixture thereof carried out with (A) 1,2-AEP, (B) 1,3-API, (C) Bis3APA, and (D) CDI membranes. The panels match the processes displayed in Fig. 3. AExM contact surface: 19.625 cm².

Fig. 7. The efficiency of extraction in the hybrid catalytical dialysis process according to the type of feed solution and the type of membrane.

the work reported in this paper. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper].

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Data availability

I shared the link of my data

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